

Fermat's Principle and Loss of Information

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Noether's theorem associates an invariance with a conserved quantity. In the case of the 2-dimensional Snell's law example, with an n_1 - n_2 (index of refraction) interface along the x axis, there is invariance in x associated with a conserved $p(x)$ (momentum in the x direction). One may use this result, together with $E=p_1c/n_1=p_2c/n_2$ ((1)) to obtain Snell's law without any consideration of Fermat's principle, i.e. a maximization equation as seen in (1).

This begs the question: Why should one consider Fermat's principle. We argue that given the constraint (1) which is based on numbers not vectors, one might wish to obtain Snell's law without any use of vectors. One may note that one has $p(x), p(y)$ and p (magnitude) as well as x, y, r in each medium. These two triangles coincide. The information contained in (1) is based on a number (i.e. magnitude). Other examples of numbers in the problem are distance and time, with $d=vt$ in each medium, where $v=c/n_i$ for a photon. One may notice that these numbers are linked with the triangle $(p(x), p(y), p)$ and so carry this information, but one also requires information about n_i . If one considers a problem in which one tries to find the appropriate triangle (i.e. $p(x), p(y)$) which is linked to the same (x, y) triangle, then one may consider moving the x point because it has invariance. The question then becomes: What number should be associated with this movement of x ? Should one use d or t ? Using d bypasses n_i information, while t includes it, thus it seems that t contains information about n_i as well as the vector x, y . Given the number of choice, t , which is linked to x , what should one do with it? Moving x creates two different triangles, one in each n_i medium.

Thus, $t(x)=t_1(x)+t_2(x)$ seems to be a superset of x -information, which contains buried information of the vector components $(p(x), p(y))$ or x, y . If one believes that one has a condition linked to a subset of the superinformation, namely x -component information, then this must be extracted. We suggest that d/dx extracts this information (and is also the generator of the invariance in x). Then, the subset information condition becomes:

$$dt_1/dx + dt_2/dx = 0 \quad ((2))$$

In other words, the 0 in ((2)), usually associated with maximization also implies 0 net x component information in one medium versus the other, a subset of overall x information. This approach is linked to free particle quantum mechanics, as we have argued before, because d/dx may also act on $p(x)$ to yield the information $p(x)$.

Snell's Law

As shown in (1), one may obtain Snell's law by considering:

$$E=p_1(c/n_1)=p_2(c/n_2) \text{ and } p_1(x)=p_2(x) \quad ((3))$$

If θ is an angle made with the y axis and the n_1 - n_2 interface is along the x , then:

$$p_1 \sin(\theta_1) = p_2 \sin(\theta_2) \rightarrow n_2/n_1 = \sin(\theta_1)/\sin(\theta_2) \quad ((4))$$

There is no need for Fermat's principle or $d/dx F(x)=0$ to obtain ((4)). There is, however, the need to use vectors and to know that $p_1(x)=p_2(x)$.

We suggest that one may use numbers (functions of x) and the idea of loss of information to bypass the use of vectors and the conservation law. In other words, the conservation of the x -component of momentum is linked to x -invariance (Noether's theorem), but here we argue that it may be expressed as a loss of information, i.e. x component information in one medium must match that in the second. The issue is that x -component information is a subset of overall x information.

Use of a Number

((3)) is based on the use of a vector and there is a clear pictorial showing a triangle in each medium $p(x)$, $p(y)$, p which is identical to the triangle x,y,r . If one tries to use a number (function of x), the information contained in this triangle cannot disappear. At the same time, there is a second piece of information in the problem, namely n_i , the index of refraction, and this is linked with numbers (magnitudes). For instance:

$$E = p_1 c/n_1 = p_2 c/n_2 \text{ or } p_1 = n_1 p \text{ and } p_2 = n_2 p \quad ((5a)), \text{ but also}$$

$$d_i = c/n_1 t_1, \quad d_2 = c/n_2 t_2 \quad ((5b))$$

Both d_i and p_i (magnitudes) contain information about the triangle, but it is t (time) and not $d = \sqrt{a^2 + x^2}$ for medium 1 which retains the n_i information. Given the invariance in x , one may seek to find a suitable x . What does a suitable x mean? We suggest that one must have x component information from t_1 and t_2 match as there is no reason for one to contain different information based on the invariance of x .

Now, x component information is buried within $t_i(x)$ (the superset of x information), i.e.

$$t_1 = n_1/c \sqrt{a^2 + x^2} \quad \text{and} \quad t_2 = n_2/c \sqrt{a^2 + (L-x)(L-x)} \quad ((6))$$

Taking d/dx reveals x relative to the magnitude as both pieces contain x information. The combination of this information should be 0 because a minus appears in the t_2 term. There should be no net x information due to the invariance in x .

$$dt_1/dx + dt_2/dx = 0 = n_1 x / \sqrt{a^2 + x^2} - n_2 (L-x) / \sqrt{a^2 + (L-x)(L-x)} \quad ((7))$$

((7)) is also Snell's law.

Extension To Quantum Mechanics

Given that $dt/dx = p(x)$, one may construct a different function which carries this same information:

$$p(x) x \quad ((8))$$

This is information with d/dx picking out a specific component, just like t is overall x information, but d/dx picks out the x component. Thus, one might suggest that if $p(x)x$ is information, it should be linked to a probability:

$$\exp(i p(x) x) \text{ which does not grow or shrink indefinitely } ((9))$$

Taking \ln of ((9)) and then $-id/dx$, picks out the conserved quantity, just in Fermat's approach.

Thus, information may be quite general and one may use an operator d/dx to obtain a specific portion of this more general information because one may make direct statements about it. For instance in the Fermat case, one may argue that the x -components of the n_1 and n_2 triangles cancel because due to x invariance, they cannot represent different x -component information.

Thus, there is an overall general information $p(x)x$ and a component specific one $p(x)$ obtained from the general one using d/dx or $-id/dx$ in the quantum case, we argue.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we try to argue that Fermat's principle is linked to the idea of information contained in a function, even if vectors/triangles appear in a problem. The key point is to choose a function which contains all of the information, i.e. triangles $(p(x), p(y), p)$ and n_i (index of refraction) overall information. This leads to the use of t . Thus, $t(x)$ is overall information (superset of information), but we argue that one may consider that only a portion of this information is linked with an invariance rule, i.e. invariance in x which is an x -component idea. One may obtain this subset of information through $d/dx t$ such that $dt_1/dx + dt_2/dx = 0$ so that there is no net x -component information. In other words, there is vector information buried within $t(x)$ and one may impose invariance conditions on this due to x -invariance. Thus, d/dx is an operator which extracts a certain type of information about x -components from a more general x -information function, namely $t(x)$, we argue.

References

1. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Snell%27s_law